

THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORIENTAL MINIATURE DURING THE TIMURID PERIOD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7583410>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 18th January 2023

Accepted: 29th January 2023

Online: 30th January 2023

KEY WORDS

*Miniature art, Oriental
miniature, period of
development, Timurid period.*

ABSTRACT

*This article will talk about the stages of development of
Oriental miniature art and the importance of the
Timurid era in this process.*

Oriental miniature is distinguished by a huge position in the history of World Culture. It embodied the artistic and aesthetic heritage of the peoples and descendants of the Central Asian region. Researchers interpret the history of miniature art in murals and in the person of fairy-tale legend characters from ancient books. For historians and ethnographers, this incomparable source testifies to unique information about the cultural and material way of life of people of past centuries. Alchemy is a kind of heritage that studies the ancient preparation process of such materials as varnish-paint.

Miniature art as a masterpiece of the East is closely intertwined with medieval literature. The researchers found that this is a free view of the ancient art form-the coverage of the content of the literature of the Great East by means of an image.

Only with the help of these means of art did the content and form of medieval works express themselves. Those who created these works showed a deep understanding of Oriental literature and the height of their own mental thinking with the help of specific artistic means in miniature. Acquaintance with Oriental miniatures, acquaintance not only with beauty, but also understanding the sources of modern oriental art, serves as the foundation.

Oriental miniature has come a long and complex path throughout its development. In the history of Oriental miniature art, there is a four-century period that unites a number of schools:

1. Timurid period Khorasan and Movarounnakh (Herat, Samarkand, Tabriz, Sheroz schools)
2. Savafid period-Iran (Sheroz, Tabriz, Mashhad, Isfahan schools)
3. Shaybanid period - Central Asia (Bukhara, Samarkand schools)
4. Baburid period-India (Agra, Dexli schools)
5. Miniature centers of Central Asia of the XVII-XX centuries.

The emergence of the Timurid dynasty was associated with the name of Amir Timur, which lasted from 1370 to 1506. In the history of the peoples of Central Asia, the Timurid

period is characterized by the development of its culture. In history, the role of the individual always stood high. Our grandfather Amir Timur was a great person. He introduced to the world the power of the Turkic people and the state. After Timur, Turkestan was divided into small khanates, in the middle there was a crown-throne, amal Talish, gurukhbazites, tensions increased. Timur has done great work for the prosperity and future of his state, which he created with his ACL. Famous scientists, architects, mohir khunarmands and binoculars were brought to cities such as Samarkand, Kesh, Shahrisabz, Bukhara. In the cities of Samarkand and Shakhrisabz, especially magnificent structures were built. The ambassador of the king of Castile, Clavixo, had written that "this yyer hama thing would be annealed in gold, lojuvard and other noble colors, and that it was good for Paris, who was also great masters of the letter."

During the reign of Amir Timur, a kind of miniature School of painting was decided in Samarkand, - writes academician olima G.A. Pugachenkova. An extract from the XIV-Khvasr and a small composition of individuals, trees, flowers, flanked with delicacy in miniature copies of khomush, were put into paper by ingenious Masters in nihoyat, and apprentice artists were engaged in the work of copying them.

The founder of the Timurid school in the Fine Arts was considered the Master Gunch. His student was a Steam Master Jahangir. The master Jahangir Pir Sayid had mentored Akhmad Tabrizi. Musavvir Kamoliddin Bekhzad, who left a worthy mark not only in the East, but also in the art of the whole world, learned the secrets of art from Pir Sayid Akhmad Tabrizi. Along with this, Behzod, who was an early loser from his parents, was brought up by the great painter of Herat, Amir Rukhillo (Mirak Naqosh), who taught the secrets of painting and miniature in Niguristan (Academy of Arts).

A unique painting of miniature Oriental fine art is also directly related to his works during the Timurid period. In this period, together with religious books, Khafiz, Bedil, Saadi, Jami. The extioj to the Navoi Giants was great. The hattots who copied the manuscript, the famous hattots who were brought from other Eastern countries, the minatourists of musavvir and the muzahkhibs worked together.

The scientist Kazi Akhmad had written about these miniature artists in terms of artists and deeds: "it turns out that the thoughts and ideas of these masters of art that leave a person in awe are known in all regions and have the attention of all educated people. What Hech of the Axl of art was not endowed with such a powerful subtlety of thought and talent as in the Companions of this mustache. No one can bring the images that are finding their expression in the walls of the fountain into the mirror of such beauty."

Beautiful samples of manuscripts created during the reign of Timur and Ulugbek testify to the high skill of musavvir, Hattot, Naqqash and others who worked during this period. Based on the fact that each of the master creators who worked on the manuscript of the book perfectly mastered his profession, in the Timurid ERA, this yyer indicates that art has risen to an unprecedented pogona. In the XIV-XV centuries, several mature miniature schools arose, and almost all of this was located in the Centers of the Timurid state: Bogdod, Sheroz, Tabriz, Herat and Samarkand.

From the beginning of the 15th century, a new stage begins in the development of Oriental miniature. The main reason for this is the centralized system of states of the Timurid

Empire. Timur, who ruled in Movarounnahr in 1365, drives the Mongols out of Central Asia. Conquered the countries of Khorezm and the Baltic. Then preparations began for the journey of Iran, Iraq, Syria, Turkey, India. At the beginning of the 16th century, Timur established a large state on the territory from the Mediterranean Sea to India. Relations were established with the countries of the East and West Yyeuropa. Information about these can be seen in the memoirs of the Spanish ambassador to Samarkand, Clavicho de Gonzalez. He describes Samarkand as "the light - emitting point of the globe." International trade is gaining momentum, the capital becomes a center of science, culture and art. Outstanding scientists and literary figures, architects and architects, artists and artists were brought to movarounnakhr. As a result, the artistic cultures of the peoples of the Middle East and Asia were added, laying the foundation for a new method in art.

Even after Timur's death, Samarkand remained a center of Science and culture under the leadership of his grandson Ulugbek. Herat culture was also among them, and the country was ruled by Timur's son Shahrukh Mirzo. At the end of the 14th and beginning of the 15th centuries, large miniature painters created the Timur Palace in Samarkand. In particular, historical sources are based on the fact that the Bogdod master Abdulhai Shuhrat, the head of the Samarkand art workshops, won. The biography of Central Asian artists according to Muhammad Dost's education had since written "according to his style, no other person could write". Friend Muhammad, - Hech could not bypass the style of a painter Abdulhai, all sought to draw in this style. Sheikh Mohammed Taliliy, Pir Akhmad Bogi Shamali, Muhammad Ibn Makhmudshukh Al Khayyam, who created during this period, are also the disciples of Abdulhai".

During the time of Timur's nabera Mirzo Ulugbek (1409-1449), miniature art was highly developed. Its name is famous not only as the king of khukmron, but also as a major scientist and patron of science, art. During his reign, the city was characterized by its construction, architecture, artistic ugliness, the flowering of literature and art. The main interest of Ulugbek was the field of Astronomy, on the side of which famous scientists were attracted, and a famous observatory was built in Hech Kaier, which could not be equated with him. Ulugbek miniaturanavis also supported the creativity of the artists. Even in this competence, the street of musavvirs in Samarkand was "Kui-Naqoshon".

In conclusion, relying on the opinions of historians and art historians, we can say that in the Timurid period of the 15th century, science and art were highly developed in Central Asian cities such as Samarkand, Herat, Bukhara, and this direct art culture also had a huge impact on the prospect of Oriental miniature. After all, the role of Alisher Navoi and Kamoliddin Behzod among the cultural figures of that time is incomparable.

References:

1. A. Madraimova, N. Normatov. Sharq miniatyura maktablari (maqolalar to'plami)
2. Валиев, А. Н., Туланова, Д. Ж., & Гуломова, Н. Х. (2018). Современные педагогические и инновационные технологии обучения на занятиях по черчению. Молодой ученый, (3), 183-184.
3. Туланова, Д. Ж., & Гуломова, Н. Х. (2018). Технология и условия проведения дидактических игр в процессе преподавания черчения в вузе. In Образование как

фактор развития интеллектуально-нравственного потенциала личности и современного общества (pp. 89-93).

4. Jabborova Shahzoda Husen qizi (2022) Vizual faoliyat jarayonini boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari ta'lim jarayonida qo'llash. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI JURNALI 15(02) 24-27.

5. Aslanova Nargiza Hakimovna (2021) Tasviriy San'at Fani To'garaklarida STEAM Talim Tizimi. Journal of Innovations in Social Sciences 01(06) 2021 99-106.

6. Jabborova Shahzoda Husen qizi (2022) TASVIRIY SAN'AT DARSLARIDA NAZARIY BILIMLARNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI. O'QUVCHILAR IJODIY FAOLIYATIGA TA'SIRI. "ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ" ISSN: 2658-7989 05.04.2022.

7. Umurova Maftuna Uyg'un qizi (2022) DEKORATIV SAN'AT VA UNING O'QUVCHILAR BADIY ESTETIK DIDIGA TA'SIRI. "ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ" ISSN: 2658-7989 05.04.2022.